

A short overview on fluorescent nanoclusters and its application in sensing of metal ions[†]

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Abstract : The fluorescence of noble metal nanoclusters (NCs) has attracted burgeoning interest among the chemists working in the field of sensors and biosensors development due to their unique properties such as excellent photostability, low toxicity, bio-compatibility and size-dependent fluorescence. The size of noble metal NCs is between metal atoms and nanoparticles, and comparable to the Fermi wavelength of electrons, which resulting in the molecule-like properties and discrete energy levels to show size-dependent fluorescence. Because of the excellent fluorogenic properties, the noble metal NCs are widely used for the development of fluorescent probes for various applications. This short review was narrated to summarize some selected applications of noble metal NCs (mainly of gold and silver) in the detection of metal ions.

Keywords : Fluorescent nanoclusters, fluorescent probes, metal ions, gold nanoclusters, silver nanoclusters.

Introduction

There is an increasing demand for the detection of ionic analytes in the chemical environments, both inside the living systems and surrounding environment. Research on the recognition, sensing and extraction of metal ions of biological and environmental importance has keenly attracted scientists owing to the ubiquitous distribution in the environmental, industrial and biological processes. Metal ions are involved in cellular and subcellular functions¹ and can effectively control the enzyme-catalyzed reactions². Thus, the intake of essential (Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Fe^{3+} etc.) and non-essential (Cd^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Al^{3+} etc.) metal ions in proper amount in the body is necessary as their disproportion may lead to toxicity and cause a threat to human health through cellular toxicity, liver and kidney damage, and neurodegenerative diseases and so on³.

Owing to these increasing detrimental effects on the environment and living systems, there has been a growing interest in the development of analytical

methods that allows rapid, selective and inexpensive determination of metal ions in aqueous medium. Therefore, the finding of new metal ions selective receptors is an important goal which involves sensors development for environmental remediation, selective separation and extraction of chemical species. Various methods adopted for the detection of these ions are atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS), ion chromatography, electrochemistry, stripping voltammetry and inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometry (ICP-AES) etc.⁴⁻⁶. However, these techniques are expensive, requires significant and sophisticated instrumentation, non-portable and complicated sample pre-treatment methods. Thus, the selective and sensitive sensing of metal ions by optical chemosensors in the proximity of supramolecular chemistry have considerably gained research interest in terms of their potential applications⁷. As described in Fig. 1, the chemosensor generally possess two important components : a receptor for the selective recognition of target analyte, a light-emitting group (fluorophore)

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that provides detectable optical response upon analyte recognition. In the recent few decades, many optically active chemosensors were developed for the selective detection of metal ions by using various organic fluorophores and receptors like azo-derivatives⁸, anthrylacetamide⁹, crown-ethers¹⁰, dithiocarbamate¹¹, naphthalimides¹², rhodamine¹³, anthraquinone¹⁴, fluorescein¹⁵, etc. However, many of these reported organic based chemosensors works in organic solvents or mixed organic-aqueous medium and thus, lacks selectivity and sensitivity in on-site monitoring of analyte in aqueous biological and environmental systems.

Fig. 1. General approaches for the designing of optical chemosensors.

From the last two decades, the nanotechnology-derived optically active materials such as semiconductor quantum dots, polymer dots, carbon dots, noble metal nanoparticles/nanoclusters (NPs/NCs) provides an alternate to organic based chemosensors and becomes an emerging candidate to increase portability, enhance stability, selectivity, sensitivity of sensors and analytical measurement technologies. Variation in the properties of nanomaterials to that of bulk differs in the redox properties, band gap, enhancement in toughness and strength, anomalous melting points and unusual crystal structures (in metals) which results from smaller sizes, including the quantum size effect on photochemistry, non-linear optical properties of semiconductor or the emergence of metallic properties with the size of the particles¹⁶. Among the various nanomaterials, the noble metal nanoparticles/nanoclusters (NPs/NCs) are widely applied in the field of sensor and biosensors development because of the one-pot easy synthesis and surface modification with

suitable organic molecules for target specific detection of analytes from the aqueous medium.

Fluorescent metal nanoclusters

Recently, innovations to produce non-toxic nanoparticles smaller than ~ 2 nm in diameter of metals (Au/Ag) have been made successful where the size approaches the Fermi wavelength of an electron (~ 2 nm), which is the De Broglie wavelength of an electron at the Fermi-level. These ultra-small nanoparticles have been classified as the new class of nanomaterials called nanoclusters (NCs) that exhibit properties that fundamentally differ from plasmonic counterparts owing to the quantum size effects and extremely high surface-to-volume ratio. Precisely, noble metal nanoclusters (e.g. Au, Ag) have been attracting attention for their unique role in bridging the “missing link” between atomic and nanoparticle behaviour¹⁷. These sub-nanometre particles demonstrate molecular-like electronic transitions¹⁸ between HOMO-LUMO energy levels due to their ultra-small finite cluster size¹⁹. As a result, the energy transitions can be rationalized according to the jellium model ($E_{\text{fermi}}/N^{1/3}$)²⁰. Although, the exact photoluminescence (PL) mechanism of metal NCs remains unknown and unexplored, it has been suggested that their luminescence is highly dependent on the size of the metal cores and surface ligands²¹. These metal NCs can produce multitudinous measurable signals, such as luminescence and chemiluminescence, and have some distinctive features such as ultrafine size with narrow size distribution, and good photo-stability and biocompatibility.

The ultra-small size of the NCs also allows the ligand shell and the surface of the metal core to significantly contribute to their physical and chemical properties. The two possible mechanisms that could be used to explain the observed emission from these small metal clusters intra-band (sp/conduction band) transition and inter-band (d-sp) transition. The small and tuneable core-shell structure of the NCs can facilitate their interaction with the analytes, especially small molecules and ions resulting in improved sensor performance. Additionally, the properties of the metal core and the ligand shell in the NCs can be

independently tailored during the synthesis or through post-synthetic modifications by using different metals and organic ligands¹⁹. Moreover, the luminescent NCs often have well-defined compositions (specific molecular formulas) and structures²² that could facilitate the investigations into their sensing mechanisms because the products generated by the interaction between the NCs and the analytes could be readily analysed at the molecular level by using advanced separation and characterization techniques (e.g. high-resolution electrophoresis, mass spectrometry, and X-ray absorption spectroscopy). Thus, the fluorescence emission of NCs could be readily adjusted from the visible to near-infrared region leading to a wide range of applications, including chemical and biological sensing²³, cellular and animal imaging²⁴, as well as cancer therapy²⁵.

Synthesis of fluorescent metal nanoclusters

A broad range of luminescent metal NCs composed of gold (Au)^{23,26}, silver (Ag)^{26,27}, copper (Cu)^{26,28}, platinum (Pt)^{26,29}, bismuth (Bi)³⁰, molybdenum (Mo)³¹ or mixed metals³² have been successfully fabricated using diverse top-down or bottom-up approaches. Recently, many different synthetic approaches including radiolytic, chemical, sonochemical, photochemical and microwave methods have been developed to prepare water-soluble fluorescent NCs^{33,34} and some recent reviews appeared that discussed the synthesis of NCs in details³⁵. As the bare metal NCs are not stable for a longer period in the solution, they are typically protected by organic ligands. Thiolated, carboxylic and amine terminated ligands such as peptides, polymers, dendrimers and proteins are routinely used as protecting and stabilising agent for the synthesis and stabilization of highly fluorescent NCs due to their unique and strong interaction with noble metals, which could lead to an extraordinary stability and distinct properties of photoluminescence. This labelling of the biomolecule of fluorescent metal NCs is the key basis for their further application to specific biosensing and bioimaging which is commonly based on passive adsorption, multivalent chelation and covalent-bond formation. Important parameters for controlling the size, structure,

oxidation state and surface properties of metal NCs include the species and concentration of chemicals (ligands) or templates, the concentration of metal ions, the species and concentration of reducing agents, pH of the solution, as well as the reaction temperature and time. Various proteins, such as bovine serum albumin (BSA)^{35,36}, human serum albumin (HSA)³⁷, insulin³⁸, horseradish peroxidase³⁹, pepsin⁴⁰, lactotransferrin⁴¹, as well as lysozyme^{42,43} have been employed as templates for the preparation of the fluorescent metal NCs. Protein-directed synthesis is particularly very attractive because proteins serve as environmentally-benign reducing and stabilizing molecules, require only mild reaction conditions, and offer greater water solubility and natural bio-compatibility (Fig. 2). Furthermore, the 3D complexed structures of proteins can withstand a wide range of pH and can be easily conjugated with other systems.

Fig. 2. Protein template based synthesis of nanoclusters.

Detection metal ions with fluorescent metal nanoclusters

A strong luminescence or high QY of the NCs is crucial for realizing a good sensitivity of the fluorescent sensors. The luminescence properties (e.g. emission intensity and wavelength) of the NCs are highly sensitive to the local environment, the size and structure of the NCs that provide an excellent response for signalling their interaction with analytes. The fluorescence “turn-off”, “turn-on” and ratiometric detection are three common schemes in the NCs-based optical sensors based on analyte-induced aggregation of NCs and other mechanisms based on energy/charge/electron transfer between the analytes and NCs⁴⁴. Various AuNCs and AgNCs stabilized by proteins such as e.g. lysozyme⁴², BSA^{45,46}, GSH⁴⁷ etc. and polymers such as polyethyleneimine (PEI) have been successfully proposed for the construction of fluores-

cent recognition of metal ions in aqueous medium. In such systems, three primary interactions between the metal (Au/Ag) core and analytes have been reported: metallophilic interactions, analyte deposition on the metal core surface, and analyte-induced metal core decomposition. Highly luminescent AuNCs and AgNCs have been used to construct fluorescent sensors for a variety of chemical and biological analytes^{49–53}.

Recognition of heavy metal ions has gained significant importance due to their high toxicity can bind to various cellular components, leading to the dysfunction, harm human health. Many fluorescent NCs as sensitive sensing probes have been used to detect various heavy metal ions, such as Zn^{2+} , Ag^+ , As^{3+} , Cd^{2+} , Cr^{3+} , Cr^{6+} , Cu^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Hg^{2+} etc. based on fluorescence quenching or enhancement. For instance, the red fluorescent BSA or lysozyme templated AuNCs were used as recognition probes for Hg^{2+} based on fluorescent quenching with a very low limit of detection⁴⁶. This fluorescence quenching could be due to metallophilic interactions between Hg^{2+} and Au^+ on the Au cluster surface. By taking advantage of this $5d^{10}-5d^{10}$ metallophilic interaction between Hg^{2+} and Au^+ that alter electronic structures of AuNCs, many sensitive and selective sensing systems have been developed for the detection of Hg^{2+} ^{42,48}. Various nanoclusters for sensing of Cu^{2+} have been developed, for example, GSH-AuNCs possess carboxylic group that can readily complex with Cu^{2+} based on analyte induced fluorescence quenching with LOD was measured to be 86 nM at a signal-to-noise (S/N) ratio of 3, which is much lower than the U.S. EPA limit for Cu^{2+} in drinking water (20 μ M)⁴⁹. Although, turn-off assays may compromise specificity since other quenchers or environmental stimulus might also lead to fluorescence quenching and report “false positive” results, thus, design and development of turn-on sensor is still receiving attention. Recently, Chang and co-workers⁵⁰ had demonstrated a novel, turn-on fluorescent assay for using DNA-templated AgNCs for Cu^{2+} , wherein addition of copper ions leads to formation of DNA-Cu/Ag NCs with more complete protection from DNA templates and thus, enhances the fluorescence. The HSA-

AgNCs were synthesized by tuning the procedure in order to make them toggle between blue-emitting (Ag_9 : HSA) and red-emitting (Ag_{14} : HSA) nanoclusters. This novel probe acts as a dual sensor and can serve as luminescent turn “on” and “off” metal switches for Co^{2+} and Zn^{2+} ions, as shown in Fig. 3⁵¹. AuNCs functionalised with dicysteine shows fluorescence enhancement upon interaction with As^{3+} because the electrons can flow from the electron rich AuNCs to the electron deficient As^{3+} , resulting in an increase in the radiative decay rate of the AuNCs. The developed system provides LOD of 53.7 nM that is lower than the MAL (133 nM) of arsenic in drinking water set by the U.S. EPA⁵². Recently, some interesting nanosensors for metal ions were developed using fluorescent nanoclusters are summarized in Table 1, which indicate their potential to detect down to nanomolar level or less.

Fig. 3. Schematic representation showing the dual sensor switchable probe for Co^{2+} and Zn^{2+} using metal nanoclusters (Adapted from Ref. 51).

As described in Fig. 1, the fluorescent nanoclusters are directly applied for the sensing of analytes or applied after further covalently conjugated with suitable organic molecules. In our approaches, we have developed some nanoclusters based nanosensors by conjugating with vitamin B_6 cofactors like pyridoxal and pyridoxal 5'-phosphate. The vitamin B_6 cofactor plays crucial roles in enzymatically catalysed transaminations to form an α -keto acid and pyridoxamine 5-phosphate as well as in many other biosynthetic processes^{60,61}. Pyridoxal containing enzymes are central to numerous metabolic pathways such as decarboxylations of amino acids⁶², racemization of amino acids⁶³ and aldol type addition of the pyridoxal stabilized glycine carbanion to formaldehyde or acetaldehyde⁶⁴. Considering the ability to detect metal

Table 1. Summary of the few reported AgNCs and AuNCs based sensors for metal ions

Ions	Functionalized NCs	LOD	Ref.
	BSA-AuNCs	80 nM	53
	BSA-AgNCs	48.7 nM	54
	GSH-AgNCs	0.1 nM	55
	GSH-AuNCs	0.2 nM	56
Hg ²⁺	Lysozyme Type VI-AuNCs	3 pM	48
	AuNCs	10 nM	42
	Lipoic Acid-AuNCs	0.5 nM	57
	Lipoic Acid-AgNCs	0.1 nM	58
	Lysozyme-AuNCs	86 nM	49
Cu ²⁺	GSH and cyclodextrin AuNCs	1.3 ppm	59
	PEI-AgNCs	48.7 nM	55
Zn ²⁺	Salicylaldehyde-BSA-AuNCs	0.1 nM	56
Cr ⁶⁺	Polyethyleneimine-AgNCs	0.2 nM	57
As ³⁺	Cysteine-AuNCs	53.7 nM	52

ions by the Schiff base derivatives of vitamin B₆ derivatives^{65,66}, we have designed and developed vitamin B₆ cofactor (pyridoxal/pyridoxal-5-phosphate) conjugated fluorescent nanoclusters such as AuNCs/AgNCs templated with proteins (BSA/Lysozyme) or polymers (PEI) for turn-on or turn-off sensing of metal ions like Hg²⁺, Zn²⁺ and Cd²⁺ in aqueous medium⁶⁷⁻⁶⁹. The reported luminescent gold nanoclusters was first

synthesized using BSA as a template and then conjugated with the vitamin B₆ cofactor pyridoxal (Py)⁶⁷. The free amines present in the coated BSA react with the aldehyde group of pyridoxal and formed the pyridoxal conjugated BSA-AuNCs. The developed pyridoxal conjugated BSA-AuNCs system was successfully applied for the selective fluorescent detection of Hg²⁺ in aqueous medium with low limit of detection in comparison with the reported papers⁵³. For real on-site detection, the paper-based analytical technology was developed for the sensing of Hg²⁺ in water via covalent anchoring of the nanosensor onto the cellulose paper as shown in Fig. 4. The paper-based sensors offer portability and operational simplicity by physisorption of molecular sensors and can be applied in many applications such as bio-diagnosis, water and seafood control as well as environmental markers. Similar to the Py_BSA-AuNCs approach, red fluorescent gold nanoclusters (Lyso-AuNCs) using lysozyme and them conjugated with the vitamin B₆ cofactor pyridoxal-5'-phosphate (PLP)⁶⁸. Upon addition of PLP, the red fluorescence of Lyso-AuNCs changed to yellow due to the formation of a Schiff base between the -CHO group of PLP and the free -NH₂ present in the lysozyme (Fig. 5). Once the PLP

Fig. 4. (a) The paper-based device prepared by the covalent modification with the pyridoxal conjugated BSA-AuNCs, (b) fluorescence color changes visualized on test paper strips of Py_BSA-AuNCs upon interaction with different concentrations of Hg²⁺ (1 mM to 1 nM) observed under UV light at 365 nm and (c) the XPS spectrum of Py_BSA-AuNCs before and after addition of Hg²⁺ (Inset showing the XPS spectrum of the Au 4f band and Hg 4f band) (Adapted from Ref. 67).

was conjugated with the Lyso-AuNCs, the nano-assembly PLP_Lyso-AuNCs was applied for the detection of metal ions. The yellow fluorescence of PLP_Lyso-AuNCs turned to bluish-green fluorescence giving a significant turn-on fluorescence at 475 nm selectively in the presence of Zn^{2+} due to the complexation-induced aggregation of nanoclusters. With this system, the Zn^{2+} can be detected down to 39.2 nM. Further, the nanoprobe was validated for the detection of Zn^{2+} in various real samples. In addition, the system was applied to monitor the intracellular Zn^{2+} in live HeLa cells.

Polyelectrolytes such as polyethyleneimine (PEI) is a positively charged hyper-branched polyamine regarded as an ideal template to modify and stabilize nanoparticles based on several advantages : firstly, PEI contains primary, secondary and tertiary amine groups, which could efficiently chelate with metallic nucleus

and stabilize these particles against flocculation by the strong columbic interaction due to the inherent high cationic density of the polymer. Thus, taking advantage of the nature of PEI, we have recently developed a nano-assembly, where the vitamin B₆ cofactor PLP was conjugated over the surface of the fluorescent PEI-AgNCs and then applied for the fluorescent turn-on sensing of Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} ⁶⁹. The PLP conjugation was achieved due to the formation of a Schiff base upon interaction with the aldehyde group of PLP and the free amines present in the PEI-AgNCs (Fig. 6). This PLP conjugated nanoprobe showed a complexation-induced turn-on fluorescent response in the presence of Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} with the detection limit down to $50.8 \times 10^{-8} M$ for Zn^{2+} and $58.0 \times 10^{-8} M$, respectively. This reversible fluorescent nano-assembly with remarkable sensitivity have been successfully employed for the real samples analy-

Fig. 5. Schematic representation showing interaction of Zn^{2+} ions with conjugated Lyso-AuNCs and its intracellular detection (Adapted from Ref. 68).

Fig. 6. (a) Schematic representation showing the mechanism for interaction of Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} with developed conjugated nanoprobe PLP_PEI-AgNCs, (b) fluorescence emission spectra and (c) bar graph at 475 nm representing sensor reversibility upon interaction with EDTA. (d) The photographic images of the vials showing the reversibility in solution and DVS modified cellulosic strips (Adapted from Ref. 69).

ses in the quantitative detection of Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} in various real samples⁶⁹. In addition, using the DVS, the chemically-modified cellulosic strips were developed using the PLP_PEI-AgNCs and applied for the sensing of Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} .

Conclusions and perspectives

The unique physicochemical properties of noble metal fluorescent NCs have gained wide applications in the diversified field including sensors and biosensors development. This short review was narrated to present an overview of the properties, synthesis and their applications for the detection of metal ions. Various small molecules, proteins, polyelectrolytes etc. are used for the direct one-pot synthesis of noble metal fluorescent nanoclusters and applied for the sensing of metal ions. The direct interaction of metal ions on the surface of nanoclusters with the coated molecules and/or the metal core mostly leading to the quenching of the fluorescence by various mechanisms. Considering the advantages of fluorescent 'turn-on' sensor, the further conjugation of nanoclusters with suitable organic molecules may provide new directions for the design of turn-on sensors. Such conjugation may also provide extra-stability to the nanoclusters. With this review, we observed that despite many reports on the synthesis and applications of fluorescent NCs, there is a need of deeper research for the development of common and efficient route for the synthesis of different types of NCs with improved stability and quantum yield. Further research is also required to understand the signal-generation mechanisms from the NCs upon interaction with analytes. With the further research and development, the noble metal NCs will provide the novel analytical approaches for the monitoring of metal ions in environmental and biological samples as well as create new directions for understanding the various medical and environmental complexity raised due to the metal ions toxicity.

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